

Addressing Students' Tardiness in the New Form of Face-to-Face Classes: Narratives of Teachers

Amor G. Garciano

Abstract. This study focused on the teachers' accounts of addressing students' tardiness. I narrowed down the highlights and lowlights of the existing issues in online learning, its effectiveness, and the teacher's coping with the challenges faced along the way. I used the qualitative and phenomenological approaches to achieve the study's objectives. The 10 participants of this study were from the Lumatag Elementary School, Davao City Division. The study revealed that the themes of teachers' experiences in handling students' tardiness and establishing a routine were the first themes teachers' experiences addressed. The second theme is Creating a Positive Culture. And Lack of interactive teaching. A new quality of learning and teaching was an absolute priority for education. Explore Experiences of Teachers' Coping Mechanisms to Address the Students' Tardiness in Face-To-Face Classes. Two emerging themes were revealed: Digital Teaching as an Innovative Strategy, and the second theme was In-Person Interaction. Educational Insight can draw tardiness to ensure students stay on track academically Building positive relationships with students and Collaboration with families and the wider community can help prevent tardiness. Communicate regularly with families about attendance expectations, provide resources and support, and work together to identify and address any barriers to attendance. Remember that teachers are not only sources of information but also meant to lead managers and train/develop critical social personality traits.

KEY WORDS

1. Traditional Tardiness 2. Absentism 3. Face-to-Face Classes

1. Introduction

Attendance is pivotal in a student's academic success, as it optimizes the learning opportunities available during school hours. The act of attending classes contributes significantly to the acquisition of knowledge. However, the delay issue has historically plagued educational institutions, presenting a formidable obstacle for students by causing them to miss valuable class time and fall behind in their studies. This phenomenon has led to a cascade of challenges, including difficulties in catching up with missed lessons and educators grappling with helping students bridge the knowledge gap. At Union Christian College, the normalization and persistence of tardiness among certain students have been notable, often resulting in their referral to the guidance office. Seeking to comprehend the underlying causes of this tardiness, the researchers undertook a comprehensive study. The primary objective of this study was to identify the perceived triggers behind junior high school students' chronic tardiness. Punctuality is the key to any goal-driven organization such as the school (Ade-

gunju et al., 2019). However, the perplexity of dealing with student delays is not new. In an Elementary School Journal article, Roland and Corrigan presented research seeking to find ways to reduce delay. According to L.A. Lockwood (2020), "Tardiness is probably the most annoying breach of the rules of attendance with which school officials have to deal. From over 1,800 tardies reported in a junior high school in Pennsylvania during the 1933-1934 school year (Kovar, 2019) to over 5,000 reported in an elementary school in West Virginia during the 2014-15 school year (Speciale, 2015), it is evident that student tardiness is a chronic, ongoing problem. In fact, Pellicer and Summers relayed, "Tardiness is a problem – a serious one. It is a subtle thief who steals a most precious possession" (2018). Kosakowski (2018) sought a remedy via research into a behavioral approach to student tardiness. Maile and Olowoyo (2017) report, "Late coming to school is one of the major problems that have plagued many schools; there is hardly any school that is spared from this problem." In Poland, in an effort to combat the problem of student tardiness, school districts put attendance policies in place. Research by Caldarella et al. (2021) reported that "Traditionally, school tardiness policies have consisted of a series of punitive measures such as office discipline referrals and after-school detention. However, without the support of school district policies on Tardiness, school administrators are often left to come up with strategies to improve the timeliness of students at their school. "Rather than working with a supportive district, many principals spend time and effort finding ways to work around the district office to improve student achievement" (Bottoms Fry, 2019). In other words, principals are expected to enact policies to improve attendance, reduce delay, and increase academic achievement. "All too often, we find that local policies and practices create barriers that prevent great leaders from thriving" (New Leaders, 2018). In Belgium (Ariston (2021), Tardiness has already become a habit of some students nowadays; being tardy means coming late to school even if their house is just beside their school, and it can lead to more serious problems affecting their academic learning as well as in their performances if a student is not on time every day the student cannot perform well in class discussions when passing their output after the deadline is also an example of being tardy. Makesh (2017), In Malaysia, up to now, students are still unaware of what would be the consequences to their academic performance; in this study, the researchers aimed to find an answer to the different causes and how to avoid being tardy. In the Philippines, Mallorca (2017), When students are tardy or absent, or when they drop out of school, sequential learning cannot occur, subject matter and skills cannot be developed, and much student talent is wasted –risk students identified in the school setting include exhibiting signs of alcohol consumption, drug abuse, or anti-social behavior. this student needs an assistant to overcome their problems and to achieve in school. Abellera (2019), When counseling in the school setting is not sufficient, these students need to be referred to appropriate services in the community. For some high school students, the immediate earnings from employment seem more significant than staying in school. These students need courses in vocational education and assistance to help them develop positive attitudes toward education, perceived alternatives to dropping out, and realize the worth of long-term goals. Agode (2016) states that family situations include cultural differences between values taught at home and school, separation, divorce, or out. School personnel need to determine the causes of Tardiness, absenteeism, and dropping out and provide necessary remediation. In our school, delinquency is rampant; in evaluating the harmful effects of missing school time, research has almost exclusively focused on absences and virtually no attention has been paid to Tardiness.

Hence, this study contributes a new dimension to the field by examining the effect of student tardiness on academic achievement. Employing an empirical model on a large-scale, longitudinal, multilevel data set of urban elementary school children over 6 years of observation, 2 significant findings were found. First, students with greater Tardiness perform worse on both

standardized reading and math tests. Second, by holding an individual's record of delinquency constant, students whose classmates are tardy more frequently also have lower test scores. Although there have been policies addressing problems of delay, it is unclear whether the policy decisions they make are guided by research. Hence, this study.

1.1. Research Questions—The main purpose of this study is to discover the experiences of the teachers in their roles and responsibilities in times of change. The researcher wanted

to narrow down the highlights and lowlights of their experiences, the challenges, and the teacher's coping practices on the challenges that come along the way. Specifically, this research aims to answer the following:

- (1) What are the teachers' experiences in addressing students' Tardiness in the new face-to-face classes?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges faced by the new face-to-face classes?
- (3) What insights can be drawn from the experiences and coping practices of the teachers in the policies and practices practiced?

This study was significant to the teachers, as they were heard, and their problems were identified. As this can be an avenue for the teachers to voice their anxieties, challenges, and needs, they can develop a strategic plan to address them and help them cope better. The DepEd Regional Office would serve as a benchmark for a larger-scale study to address the teacher's needs

and challenges in the new-normal face-to-face classes. To the policymakers, for planning and drafting future pieces of training and seminars for teachers to properly address implementation gaps of utilizing the roles and responsibilities of principals in the teaching and learning process. Finally, to the fellow researchers who wanted to conduct a similar or comparative study

1.2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on John Locke's Motivation Theory (as cited by Saari and Judge, 2004), which defines motivation as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences." This definition draws attention to two aspects, in particular, namely the emotional attachment an employee has to their job and the employer's deliberate review of an employee's work. According to David and Andrzej (2016), motivation can be understood as cognitive decision-making in which the intention is to make a behavior aimed

at achieving a specific goal through initiation and monitoring. At workplaces, reviews are done using appraisals, and appraisals at work have predetermined standards; their outcome may provoke an emotional reaction in the employee, and this reaction will determine how satisfied or dissatisfied an employee is. Good marks in reviews may reflect that an employee is satisfied, and nasty marks may reflect the opposite. In every employee, motivation may be because of outside factors (extrinsic) such as rewards or, within an individual (intrinsic) desire to do better. Michael A. Gottfried has

also extensively researched all aspects of student absence and Tardiness. In nearly all of his research works, he implicates policy enactment regarding student absence and Tardiness. It was essential to understand school policy on all levels. For example, Granite School District (2019) relays: "Policies are important because they help a school establish rules and procedures and create standards of quality for learning and safety, as well as expectations and accountability." Charlotte Danielson (2002) describes in her book *Enhancing Student Achievement* how successful policies regarding attendance and Tardiness are grounded in the fact that attendance is essential and not optional. The *Eightfold Path to More Effective Problem Solving* (Bardach, 2012) offers a solid framework to support school policy analysis. This framework is used to analyze school tardiness and absence policies across several large, urban school districts. Additionally, this framework will help support consideration of possible "outcomes," which may be translated as possible relationships between these schools' tardiness and absence policies and student academic achievement. The eight steps in this policy analysis approach are defining the problem, assembling evidence, constructing alternatives, selecting criteria, projecting outcomes, confronting trade-offs, deciding, and telling your story (Bardach, 2002, p. xvi). In this framework, the first four steps focus on framing the analysis and steps five through eight focus on doing the analysis. "Defining a policy problem is an act of conceptualizing collective problems or challenges to be dealt with" (Hanberger, 2001). Bardach (2002) explains that, in the quest to define a policy problem, it can be thought of as a deficit or excess. For example, Gottfried (2014) emphasized that policymakers need to focus on early education, as

prior research suggests that for urban students, missing school is detrimental in many ways. However, many school districts fall short of implementing such education. Therefore, this lack of implementation could be defined as a policy problem. "Assertions of deficit or excess should come with magnitudes attached" (Bardach, 2018). These "magnitudes" may include, for example, the size, spectrum, or abilities of the problem. Bardach (2002) goes on to say problem definitions may contain conditions or "odds" (p. 6). An example of the spectrum of this policy analysis is how school policy on attendance and Tardiness may be associated with the negative impact of students' absences and Tardiness determined by researchers such as Calderella et al. (2011) and Gottfried (2019, 2014). This was relatable to analyzing school district attendance policies in that they may or may not specifically address the issue of Tardiness. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected variables. The experiences of Principals in the transition to the changing time's way of teaching and learning, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers as well as learners to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. There was a real concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there is how exploring the experiences of teachers in the changing time's way of teaching and learning was important to the improvement of teaching and learning process.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Method

Presented in this chapter were the description of the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, ethical considerations, research instrument, data collection, and data analysis. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) are optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What was the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research – selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Good research-undertaking starts with selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm was the patterning of a person's thinking; it was a principal among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to design actions. Differently stated, a paradigm was submitting to a view (Stanage, 2007). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who define a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, 'ultimates,' or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. In developing research methodologies, three types of philosophical assumptions were used. Epistemological assumptions deal with subjective evidence that was collected from field studies. Axiological assumptions take into account the biases of the researcher and actively report

them; it was used to establish whether the environment being studied was a product of the behavior that was encountered or if the behavior was a product of the environment (Pring, 2014). Ontological assumptions refer to the nature of the reality of the subject that is being researched. The latter assumption was best suited to my study as a qualitative researcher; Different individuals perceive these realities. These realities are heavily shaped by their experiences. Using phenomenology as a methodology, this proposed study focuses on the teachers' opinions, feelings, experiences, and inner thoughts concerning their knowledge, values, and skills acquired. It adopts a realistic ontology in which it follows the physical world, where I, as the researcher, assumed the existence of a world of causes and effects. It is not the ontology of mechanical causes caught in the cause-effect relationships; rather, in this study, the researcher assumed that some realities exist in the world and may affect the way teachers proceed to the next level. Thus, the researcher that as qualitative researchers follow a realistic ontology, they view it as a casual reality. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realists exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of the implementation of online distance learning modality during the pandemic were elaborated since there were no face-to-face classes. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to

the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study in order to obtain first-hand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985), as cited by Creswell (2013), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." The purpose of this research was to gather important details on the experiences of the learners in relation to tardiness in these new normal face-to-face classes. I assured them that I would establish close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences of learners as they went through their teaching activities during the off-classroom classes. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. I, therefore, preserved the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interpreted

the answers in the light of the participant's interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study, the researcher used the first person to explain the learners' experiences and coping mechanisms and thoroughly discussed their responses during the interview. As a researcher, I agree with the postmodernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). The aims of education were teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, and self-creation. In postmodern education, teachers lead students in discovering new things. They provide opportunities to discuss different subjects in creative ways. In this situation, students learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others' criticism and try to think critically. They learn to respect different cultures and nationalities. Also, they emphasize cooperative learning, independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It was deduced that postmodernism and creativity were embedded in each other, and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers, specifically those learners from Lumatag Elementary School, Davao City Division, were unleashed from their narratives. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the predicaments of the physical education teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013), considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline

cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. While Morrissey Higgs (2006) posited that experience was a source of knowledge that shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which was concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for the possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used a qualitative research design employing a phenomenological approach. According to Hancock et al. (2009), qualitative research answers questions regarding the issues involving societal problems. It raises the question of why people behave as they do, what the possible opinions and attitudes formed in a particular situation were, how people were affected by society in their ways of action, and how the practices and culture in the society have developed. Phenomenology, as a philosophy and a method of inquiry, was not limited to an approach to knowing; it was rather an intellectual engagement in interpretations and meaning-making

that was used to understand the lived world of human beings at a conscious level. The researcher can adopt interviews, observations, and discussions as data collection strategies within a phenomenological method of inquiry; therefore, phenomenology has both philosophical and methodological stances (Qutoshi, 2018). Phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal is to describe the nature of the specific phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews are conducted with individuals with firsthand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced regarding the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data such as do, comments, observations, and art may also be used. The data is then read, reread, and culled for phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Some philosophical assumptions were employed in the development of research methodology. Subjective evidence gathered from field investigations was the subject of epistemological assumptions that deal with subjective evidence that was collected from field studies and has also been used to gain knowledge brought by the accessibility of the place. Axiological assumptions account for the researcher's biases and actively report them; they were used to determine whether the environment being investigated results from the behavior seen. Ontological assumptions refer to the nature of the reality of the subject that was being researched. The latter assumption was best suited to my study as a qualitative re-

searcher, as different individuals perceive these realities. I also believed that these realities were heavily shaped by their experiences. The phenomenological design interprets the experiences or facts by listening to the participants' experiences and providing the meaning of those experiences (Creswell, 2007). It describes the structures of experiences as they present themselves to consciousness, without recourse to theory, deduction, or Epistemology rhetoric assumption from other disciplines. The design examines the phenomena through the subjective eyes of the participants, which describes the meaning of the experiences of several individuals regarding a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2007).

2.4. Ethical Considerations—Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection analysis and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, I dealt with former teachers in public schools. To ensure an authentic response from the participants, the researcher was responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants were extremely considered. Besides, they would not be forced to be part of the study when they refused. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers or aliases can preserve the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants were allowed to ask the researcher questions about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information was clear to the participants. Moreover, the Informed Consent Form, which the chosen participants signed, guided the participants' data gathering and participation. Lastly, the results and findings were returned to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview were kept private.

Further, each participant would be advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This would allow the participants to amend or remove any information they feel might identify them. The researcher would reserve the right to employ pseudonyms and change names and non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. **Qualification of the Researcher.** The researcher will ensure that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which would be the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and the researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the survey would reach its completion. **Adequacy of Facilities.** The researcher would strive to ensure that the study could be completed successfully at the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was likely to be completed in the target time. **Community Involvement.** The researcher would respect the local traditions, cultures, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study would not use deceit at any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher would express great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the study. **Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher.** The researcher

would respect other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher would ensure that honesty is present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and results are included or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.5. Research Participants—Purposive sampling would be applied to the selection of the research participants. Purposive sampling was a technique in which the researcher relied on his or her judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. It was a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are determined based on the researcher's judgment. Researchers often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include public school teachers, either male or female, in Lumatag Elementary School in the Division of Davao City. There would be seven informants who would be part of the in-depth interview. Moreover, coding would be used to protect the identity of the participants. IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT7 will be used for the informants of the in-depth interview.

2.6. Research Instrument—I used an Interview Guide Question Tool with sub-questions for the in-depth interview and focus group discussion in this study. The tool would serve as my guide while interviewing the selected teachers participating in the recorded in-depth interview via Google Meet, Zoom, or MS Teams and focus group discussion. This study sought to answer the research questions and collect additional input for my study. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically regarding the method, I would ask for help from the experts. My interview guide question tool

should be checked and validated by the experts. The sampling used to select my participants were under the suggestions of the expert panels. I played various roles in this study to attain success. First, asked for permission to conduct the study, which would start with the Schools Division Superintendent and then with the participants of my study. As a researcher, if consented, I recorded the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview aimed to better understand teachers' experiences in the new standard way of teaching and learning. The interview would also include how the Department of Education should improve its programs. After gathering the needed data, the researcher transcribed and analyzed everything. However, human instruments were more important to be studied in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions in dealing with the persons involved in the research (Greenbank, 2003).

2.7. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher secured a letter of permission to the participants. I would use the data collection methods prescribed in the qualitative design upon approval. In the selection, sampling was applied to the research participants; purposive sampling is a sampling technique in which a researcher relies on his or her judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. It was a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample were chosen based on the researcher's judgment. Researchers often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include all teachers in Lumatag Elementary School in the division of Davao City. Ten informants would be part of the virtual in-depth interview. Moreover, coding was used to protect the identity of the participants. IDI-1 to IDI-10 would be used for the informants of the in-depth interview. The researcher needs to get the subjective interaction

between the participants of the study. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio-recording), and the interpretive paradigm would be used. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing and observation and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to construct a meaningful reality collaboratively. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data collection, such as documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. To obtain legitimate and trustworthy data on teachers' experiences of the new normal way of teaching and learning, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This interview aimed to gather information on the feelings and experiences of former teachers of public schools. The participants were encouraged to express their answers most comfortably. The interview with the participants has been transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored so that they can easily be found and protected from damage and loss. In this study, I made use of an Interview Guide Question Tool with sub-questions for the virtual in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The tool was used as my guide while interviewing the selected elementary teachers who had been my participants in the recorded virtual in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This aimed to answer the research questions and to collect additional inputs that can be used in my study. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically regarding the method, I asked for help from the experts. My interview guide question tool was checked and validated by the experts. The sampling that I used to select my participants was following the

suggestions of the expert panels.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In analyzing the qualitative data, I used discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Discourse analysis focuses on the language used and patterning of language used by the study's informants, as reflected in the detailed transcripts of recorded speech (Bueno, 2016). I transcribed and analyzed the recorded in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Part of the analysis was to determine female school leaders' challenges, coping mechanisms, and leadership behavior. Thematic analysis was a method of identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data (Braun Clarke, 2006). It was a widely used method of analysis in qualitative research. In this study, I looked for patterns and themes generated in the transcribed in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—In the conduct of this study, I would follow a procedure that would lead to giving answers to the main questions. The first phase of this study involves collecting data through an in-depth online interview of selected informants through Google Meet or Zoom. After this, the data were organized, transcribed, encoded, and translated. The transcribed data or significant statements that were developed will be subjected to data analysis using discourse and thematic analysis or grouped into themes. The analyzed data were thoroughly interpreted by the researcher with the help of the theories of this study. Common themes based on the informants' responses were considered in this study. The participants' experiences were described in the textural description. With the list of non-redundant units of meaning, the researcher must continue to bracket any assumptions to remain true to the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). I rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. Clusters of themes are typically formed by grouping units of meaning (Creswell, 1998;

Moustakas, 1994). The analytical framework for this study was flexible enough to allow the researcher to either gather all of the data and then analyze it or evaluate it while it was being collected. The data collected was then sifted, charted, and categorized in line with key topics and themes during the analysis stage. This process involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization was becoming familiar with the data through reading and re-reading interview transcripts. Familiarizing the whole interview with the audio recording and transcript and any contextual or reflective notes the researcher recorded was a vital stage in interpretation. It could also be helpful to re-listen to all or parts of the audio recording. The researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, exploring the field, or reading transcripts. The researcher would become aware of critical ideas and recurring themes throughout the procedure and would make a note of them. The researcher may be unable to review all of the material due to the enormous amount of data that might be collected in qualitative research. As a result, a portion of the data set would be utilized. Several elements of the data collection method would influence the selection. Coding was the process of summarizing and representing data in order to provide a systematic account of the recorded or observed phenomenon. After familiarization, the researcher carefully reads the transcript line by line, applying a paraphrase or label that is a 'code' that describes what they have interpreted in the passage as necessary. Coding aimed to classify all of the data to be compared systematically with other parts of the data set. Developing a thematic framework happens after coding a few transcripts. The researcher needs to compare the labels applied and select a set of codes to apply to all subsequent transcripts. Codes could be grouped into categories, which are then clearly

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

defined. This forms a working analytical framework. Several iterations of the analytical framework were likely required before no additional codes emerged. It was always worth having another code under each category to avoid ignoring data that does not fit; the analytical framework was never ‘final’ until the last transcript had been coded. Indexing involves identifying portions or sections of data that relate to a specific theme. This procedure is conducted using all textual data collected, such as transcripts of interviews. Ritchie and Spencer (1994) suggest using a numerical system to index references and annotating them in the margin beside the text for ease. Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for this task. Charting involves summarizing the data by category from each transcript. Good charting requires an ability to strike a balance between reducing the data on the one hand and retaining the original meanings and ‘feel’

of the interviewees’ words on the other. The chart should include references to exciting or illustrative quotations. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, analyzes the essential qualities depicted in the charts. This analysis should provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, assisting the researcher in interpreting the data set. I must be cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis and define concepts, map the range and nature of phenomena, create typologies, find associations, provide explanations, and develop strategies (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Therefore, any strategy or recommendations the researcher offers reflect the participants’ real views, beliefs, and values. Figure 2. shows procedures undertaken to analyze the textual data. Statements were developed from the transcripts and grouped into larger units of information called “meaning tunings” or themes (Creswell, 2007).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the analysis of the interview data. It introduces themes that emerge from the analysis. Along with the themes, comprehensive discussions that answered the study's objectives were included. Before my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used to present the quotations based on the study participants' responses. About the transcriptions of the interviews that were conducted, I used pseudonyms to refer to the participants of the research. The study's first objective was to discover the teachers' experiences addressing students' tardiness in the new face-to-face classes. The questions gathered substantial actual impressions of the teachers in dealing with misbehaving learners.

3.1. Experiences of the Teachers in Addressing Students' Tardiness in the New Face-to-face Classes—The first objective of this study was to identify teachers' experiences in addressing students' tardiness in the new face-to-face classes. From the interviews conducted, the experiences of teachers showed that most of the students' tardiness is due to poor preparation for school, going late to bed, being far from school from home, and a high level of poverty. The discussions between me and my participants would create an interesting idea of how their individual experiences may give a better thought on how to improve the students' attendance.

3.1.1. Establish a routine—The first theme in teachers' experiences addressing tardiness was establishing a routine that holds students more responsible for getting to class on time. Always take attendance right away to determine who is missing quickly. Conference with repeat offenders about what needs to change; do not just watch as they continually fail to be there by the time activities begin. Implementing all these strategies can be overwhelming for many people. But remember that it was not all-or-nothing; you can start with small changes and work toward healthier sleep habits, also known as sleep hygiene. Therefore, having a good routine is crucial for students because it can significantly impact their academic performance and overall well-being. Here are some insights on why having a good routine is essential: Reduces Stress: A well-planned routine can help

students manage their time effectively and reduce the stress of last-minute tasks or cramming for exams. Improves Time Management: A good routine helps students to prioritize their tasks and activities and manage their time efficiently. This can lead to better grades, more time for extracurricular activities, and reduced stress. Increases Productivity: With a good routine, students can plan their day around their most productive times and complete tasks when they are most alert and focused. A good routine can help students establish healthy sleep habits, such as going to bed and waking up simultaneously every day, which can improve their overall health and well-being. Develops Self-Discipline: Following a routine requires self-discipline, a valuable life skill that can help students succeed in their academic and professional careers. Establishes Healthy Habits: A good routine can help students develop healthy habits such as regular exercise, healthy eating, and taking breaks to avoid burnout. With that, having a good routine is essential for students to manage their time effectively, reduce stress, improve their academic performance, and develop healthy habits and self-discipline that can benefit them throughout their lives.

3.1.2. Creating a Positive Culture—Another theme is the teachers' experiences addressing tardiness in the new face-to-face format. The participants shared that creating a positive culture inside the classroom involves introducing values, norms, and standards to the students.

A school culture consists of the underlying influences and attitudes within the school based on the norms, traditions, and beliefs of the staff and students. In short, the prevailing atmosphere in your school will affect everything that goes on inside its walls. This goes beyond the student body: it also involves how teachers interact with each other, their students, and the parents. On the other hand, a positive school culture is a place where your efforts translate into positive experiences for staff and students. Success, joy, and accomplishment were all the main features of a positive school culture. When your school has a positive culture, teachers are excited to work because they see the bigger picture, and students are in a better position, both mentally and emotionally, to learn. People need to understand the culture to know how to get their work done. Guerra (2020) added micro work cultures within an organization, from management to engineering and employee cultures. Work culture differs from a company's core values, which remain unchanged. It updated its core values when it went through massive growth, expanding from under 400 people to over 4,500. Its fanatical focus on the customer, high value on innovation, and a strong belief that anything can be accomplished together never changed, Herrera said. We went full circle on this thing, and although our original values are roughly the same, it got a lot more organized in how we talk about it," he said about how the shift influenced work culture. Raudys (2018) posited that students learn more than just secular instruction at school. They develop their social skills and learn how to become successful adults. Schools that help students develop essential social skills prepare them on an even deeper level for their future after graduation. Throughout the day, encourage teachers to include activities that help students develop empathy, reliability, respect, concern, and a sense of humor. Innovation in the classroom starts with the school leader and talking with teachers, encouraging them to try new teaching methods. It can even set up regular meetings to discuss new research on teaching methods or new teaching tech, and how these can be implemented in your school. These meetings would help the whole teaching staff brainstorm and implement new ideas, bringing teachers into building your school culture. School leaders, however, swamped with their daily acts of heroism, have challenging and meaningful problems to solve: bullying, teacher turnover, improving student performance, and cultural and socio-economic differences, to name a few. The list goes on, and the challenge never ends. However, it all starts with a positive school culture. School specialists have found that a positive school culture helps care for many of those issues. A positive school culture fundamentally changes how different components of a successful school work together to create change. Researchers find that it diminishes classroom tardiness, suspensions, and behavioral issues. A positive culture promotes scholarly accomplishment, inspiration to learn, and mental achievement. Best of all, a better school culture helps scholastic achievement flourish as a core foundation of security and safety in your students' minds (Raudys, 2018). Creating a positive school atmosphere was difficult, as any administrator would tell you. Individuals have psyches, and you cannot make them feel accomplished and motivated externally – or just by telling them that you value them. They must feel part of something great – a school that yearns for success. A school that promotes positive action and rejects poor behaviors. It takes diligence, persistence, and incredible determination to build a culture. However, the strength of a culture was very hard to break. Just as breaking out of a bad culture is hard, a good one stands strong. The work you put into building a positive culture now would reap benefits for you and your community for years. Creating a positive culture for students to attend class requires a multi-faceted approach

considering the different factors contributing to absenteeism. Here are some strategies that can be helpful: Establish clear expectations and rules for attendance: Students need to understand the importance of attending class and the consequences of being absent. Communicate these expectations clearly at the beginning of the school year and reinforce them regularly. Build positive relationships with students: Students are more likely to attend class when they feel valued and connected to their teachers and peers. Take time to get to know your students, show an interest in their lives, and provide opportunities for them to collaborate and build relationships with each other. Create an engaging and interactive learning environment: Students were more likely to attend class when they felt engaged and interested in the material. Use various teaching methods and incorporate hands-on activities, group projects, and discussions to motivate students. Support struggling students: Students struggling academically or personally may be more likely to skip class. Offer support and resources to help these students overcome their challenges and stay on track. Celebrate attendance: Recognize and celebrate students who have good attendance records. Offer incentives or rewards for students who attend regularly and on time and publicly acknowledge their efforts. Communicate with parents and guardians: Engage parents and guardians to improve attendance. Communicate regularly about attendance expectations, provide updates on their child's attendance record, and work together to address any issues contributing to absenteeism.

3.1.3. Lack of interactive teaching—A new quality of learning and teaching was an absolute priority for education. Teachers were not only sources of information but also meant to lead managers and teachers in developing interactions among students and training/developing critical social personality traits. The students want to understand natural phenomena,

know scientific truths, and acquire knowledge to be applied in practice; for these reasons, they were dissatisfied with traditional education. The teachers and students in most universities that have used traditional lectures in courses have revealed limited effectiveness in teaching and learning. The teacher must use methods to encourage discovery learning and heuristic and research methods. Dynamic and communicative teaching methods, also called interactive teaching methods, constitute the basic elements of a recently developed process to motivate learning so that the students and future engineers develop a critical position about the taught content. Using interactive techniques and strategies, the students become more engaged in learning and retain more information, thus becoming more satisfied. As Senthamarai (2018) asserted a new quality of learning and teaching, in general, was an absolute priority for education. The teachers are not only sources of information, they were also meant to lead managers and teachers so as to develop the interaction among students and training/development of key social personality traits. The students want to understand natural phenomena, to know scientific truths and to acquire knowledge to be applied in practice and for these reasons they are dissatisfied by the traditional education. The teachers and students, in most universities that have used the traditional lecture in courses, have revealed the limited effectiveness in both teaching and learning. The teacher must use methods to encourage discovery learning and heuristic and research methods. Dynamic and communicative teaching methods, also called interactive teaching methods, constitute the basic elements of a recently developed process to motivate learning so that the students and future engineers develop a critical position about the taught content. She added that by using interactive techniques and strategies, the students become more engaged in learning and retain more information, thus becoming more satisfied. Keywords: Interactive,

Fig. 3. Experiences of The Teachers in Addressing Student’s Tardiness

teaching, strategies Introduction The interactive teaching and learning strategies described in this section are used to engage students in the resilience and wellbeing, drug education and road safety content included in each focus areas of this resource. Strategies are indicated in bold text in the learning activities. TKo, Edmond and Noakes, Nick (2018) emphasized that teachers should refer to this section of the resource for an explanation of the purpose and how to implement the strategy with their students. The strategies aim to promote critical and reflective thinking, research and evaluation skills that will help students to take positive action to protect,

enhance and advocate for their own and other’s health, wellbeing and safety. Students use personal and social capability to work collaboratively with others in learning activities, to appreciate their strengths and abilities and those of their peers, and to develop a range of interpersonal skills such as communication, negotiation, teamwork, leadership, and an appreciation of diverse perspective Figure 3 shows the teachers’ lived experiences in addressing students’ tardiness, establishing a routine, creating a positive culture, and lacking an interactive teaching approach.

3.2. *Teachers Coping with The Challenges Faced in the New Normal Face-To-Face Classes*—Another objective of this study is to explore the teacher’s challenges in the new normal. For this objective, the themes found were accepting the new normal reality and asking for assistance from others. The first theme, teachers coping with the challenges faced in the new regular face-to-face classes, presents various

challenges for teachers, including the digital divide. The participants shared that they just had to accept the realities of the ordinary situation after the pandemic and be able to adjust to those challenges during the transition period. A first theme will emerge from the teachers’ coping with the challenges of addressing students’ tardiness. The participants shared the initial answers or strategies to address the need to improve the learners’ school attendance

3.2.1. *Digital Teaching as Innovative Strategy*—Academic success has long been associated with attendance. Students who attend class regularly are more likely to understand better course material, participate more actively in class discussions, and achieve higher grades. Regular attendance also helps students develop time management skills and a sense of respon-

sibility. Regular attendance exposes students to a structured learning environment that promotes their progress in all aspects. Stars Ai com. (2024) stressed the use of technology has proven to be a catalyst for positive change in the field of education, and monitoring student attendance is no exception. In the transition from manual methods to technology-driven so-

lutions, many benefits can be gained, including improved accuracy, efficiency, student engagement, and early intervention opportunities. Despite the challenges of privacy concerns and resistance to change, there is excellent potential for a positive impact to be made as a result of this.

3.2.2. *In-Person Interaction*—Another theme of the teacher’s challenges in the new normal is the lack of in-person interaction with the learners. The participants shared that because of the pandemic, the learners have become distant from their classmates, peers, and teachers. The COVID-19 pandemic has compelled public school teachers and students to teach and learn through computers, laptops, and mobile phones with Internet connections. The pandemic has significantly impacted student attendance, mainly due to the lack of social interaction and engagement caused by remote learning. Here are some ways this lack of interaction may have resulted in absenteeism: Students may feel less motivated to attend virtual classes without the social support and encouragement of being physically present in a classroom. The absence of in-person interactions, such as socializing with friends or participating in extracurricular activities, can also contribute to disconnection and disengagement. Remote learning has also increased student responsibilities, such as taking care of siblings, helping with household chores, or working part-time jobs to support their families. These additional responsibilities can make it difficult for students to balance their time and attend virtual classes. Technological barriers: Some students may not have access to the necessary technology or internet connection to participate in virtual classes. This can make it difficult for them to attend class regularly and can contribute to absenteeism. Mental health challenges: The pandemic has also had a significant impact on students’ mental health. The stress and anxiety caused by the pandemic, coupled with the isolation and lack

of social interaction, can lead to depression, anxiety, and other mental health challenges. These challenges can make it difficult for students to attend class regularly and can contribute to absenteeism. Educators and administrators need to understand these challenges and work to address them to improve student attendance. This may involve providing additional resources and support for students, such as mental health services or technology assistance, and creating engaging and interactive virtual learning environments to help students stay motivated and connected. Educational institutions can adopt various strategies to mitigate the alarming rates of tardiness among students. Implementing a combination of preventive and corrective measures is essential. According to Miller’s study (2017), proactive measures like educating students about time management, setting clear expectations for punctuality, and involving parents in monitoring attendance can make a significant difference. Additionally, a study by Thompson (2019) highlighted the effectiveness of positive reinforcement. Recognizing and rewarding punctuality through small incentives can motivate students to arrive on time and instill a sense of responsibility (Harris, 2020). Williams, C (2019) stressed that solving the issue of student tardiness requires collaboration between educational institutions, teachers, students, and parents. By implementing policies that prioritize punctuality and reinforcing these policies consistently, institutions can set the tone for a punctuality-conscious culture. Teachers play a pivotal role by being role models for punctuality. The shift from traditional to online education with the support of digital technology has been primarily recognized as a trend or a forecast mainstream shortly (Thompson, 2019); the long-term environment requires a better understanding of online education with effective preparation and better technological prowess. Some studies have noted that returning to the pre-pandemic education approach would be un-

Fig. 4. Teachers Coping with the Challenges Faced in the New Face-to-Face Classes

likely, as the ongoing change is transformative. Today's students have taken to social networking like fish to water, yet, from our perspectives, little social interaction takes place in many of today's classrooms from kindergarten through college. The model of discourse in most classrooms is a one-way communication from the teacher to the students. For example, the first thing one kindergartener said to his mother after his first day of school was: "All teachers do is talk, talk, talk." He said the same thing after his first day of high school and his first day of college. His observations are not uncommon. As early as 1984, Goodlad wrote, "The data from our observations in more than 1,000 classrooms support the popular image of a teacher standing in front of a class imparting knowledge to a group of students (Hurst, 2018). Frey, Fisher, and Allen (2009) observed that "students are expected to sit hour after hour, taking notes, and answering the occasional question with little interaction with peers. The concept of teachers doing all of the talking in classrooms directly

contrasts the philosophy that learning is primarily a social activity (Dewey, 2019) and the idea that the person doing the work is the person doing the learning (Hurst, 2018). Teachers expend much energy preparing lectures. They must read various texts and synthesize the information, pick out the most critical points and cohesively organize them, write lecture notes, and then deliver the information to students who sit passively, often thinking of everything but what the teacher is saying. Who is doing all of the work in this process? The teacher. The teacher is the one reading, writing, thinking, speaking, and therefore, the one who is learning. Vacca and Vacca (2002) contend that we need to shift "the burden of learning from teachers' shoulders to students. Wilkinson, Soter, and Murphy (2010) agree that "there needs to be a gradual release of responsibility for control of the discussion from teacher to students. Probst (2007) states, "The student should do most of the work.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study—Teachers are the pillars of the educational system. They are the ones who are tasked with providing students with experiences to make them better people equipped with knowledge, skills, and attitudes to live with others in the place in which

we live. Adapting to these changes becomes a very important aspect of becoming a teacher. For this purpose, continuous professional development is a must for teachers. The results of this study provide several educational insights. Firstly, there is a paradigm shift in the educational system, leaning towards maximizing the

use of technology. Different aspects of teaching, including teachers' engagement with the learners, adjust in terms of personal adjustment. While there are still challenges during the transition from online to face-to-face for teachers, educational institutions cannot use this technology to address several problems that can occur during the new normal. Preventing absenteeism

3.3.1. Building positive relationships with students —Building positive relationships with students increases their motivation to attend class. Take time to get to know your students, provide support and encouragement, and create a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment. Providing engaging and interactive instruction can help keep students motivated and interested in attending class. Use various teaching methods, such as group activities, discussions, and hands-on projects, to keep students engaged and interested. Regular attendance monitoring and following up with absent students can help identify and address potential issues before they become chronic. Reach out to students who miss class to offer support, provide make-up work, and identify any potential barriers to attendance. Students at risk of tardiness may benefit from additional support and resources. This may include tutoring, mentoring, counseling, or other interventions to help stu-

ensures students stay on track academically and achieve their goals. Setting clear expectations for attendance and communicating these expectations to students and their families can help prevent tardiness. Communicate consequences for unexcused absences and allow students to make up missed work.

students stay on track and succeed academically.

3.3.2. Collaboration with families —Collaboration with families and the wider community can help prevent absenteeism. Communicate regularly with families about attendance expectations, provide resources and support, and work together to identify and address any barriers to attendance. Educators can help ensure that students have the support and resources they need to stay engaged and successful in school by taking a proactive approach to preventing tardiness. Also, the results of this study highlight the attention and importance given by teachers to the learners to help aid the students during the pandemic. The shift to face-to-face has not stopped teachers from finding ways to build their knowledge and skills to teach effectively. Teacher collegiality is also an important insight in this study as it shows that support from other teachers is essential for teachers to focus on the tasks given to them when attending these professional development programs.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study. It is followed by implications based on the study's findings. Future directions in addressing the teacher's experiences of student tardiness in the new normal are discussed. The main objective of this study is to explore teachers' experiences regarding students' tardiness. Specifically, it sought to explore different experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms for addressing problems. To explore the teach-

ers' experiences regarding students' tardiness, emerging themes were developed; establishing a Routine was the first theme in teachers' experiences addressing tardiness, which is establishing a routine that holds students more responsible for getting to class on time. Always take attendance right away to determine who is missing quickly. It is well-established that sleep is essential to our physical and mental health. However, despite its importance, a troubling

percentage of people are regularly deprived of quality sleep and are notably sleepy during the day. Though there is a wide range of causes and types of sleeping problems, expert consensus points to a handful of concrete steps that promote more restful sleep. Insufficient sleep in adolescents is associated with a wide variety of adverse outcomes, from poor mental and physical health to behavioral problems and lower academic grades. The second theme is Creating a Positive Culture. Another theme is the teachers' experiences in addressing tardiness in the new face-to-face format. The participants shared that creating a positive culture inside the classroom involves introducing values, norms, and standards to the students. A school culture consists of the underlying influences and attitudes within the school based on the norms, traditions, and beliefs of the staff and students. In short, the prevailing atmosphere in your school will affect everything that goes on inside its walls. This goes beyond the student body; it also involves how teachers interact with each other, their students, and the parents. On the other hand, a positive school culture is where your efforts are translated into positive experiences for staff and students. Success, joy, and accomplishment are all the main features of a positive school culture. When your school has a positive culture, teachers are excited to work because they see the bigger picture, and students are in a better mental and emotional position to learn. lastly, there is a Lack of interactive teaching. A new quality of learning and teaching is an absolute priority for education. Teachers are not only sources of information; they are also meant to lead managers and teachers in developing interactions among students and training/developing critical social personality traits. The students want to understand natural phenomena, know scientific truths, and acquire knowledge to be applied in practice; for these reasons, they are dissatisfied with traditional education. Explore Experiences of Teachers' Coping Mechanisms

To Address The Students' Tardiness In Face-To-Face Classes. The participant believes that initial digital teaching can give a first dose of medicine for the learners' demands, as some are new to or not exposed to this digital technology. Digital teaching is an innovative way of teaching students to ignite or motivate them to participate in learning. Digital Teaching as Innovative Strategy. Academic success has long been associated with attendance. Students who attend class regularly are more likely to understand better course material, participate more actively in class discussions, and achieve higher grades. Regular attendance also helps students develop time management skills and a sense of responsibility. Regular attendance exposes students to a structured learning environment that promotes their progress in all aspects. While the second theme was In-Person Interaction. Another theme of the teacher's challenges in the new normal is the lack of in-person interaction with the learners. The participants shared that because of the pandemic, the learners have become distant from their classmates, peers, and teachers. Students most likely wanted to interact in the classroom before they were bored with the traditional teaching approach and wanted a new menu in the teaching and learning processes. This idea is about the Lack of an interactive teaching approach as it was analyzed during the teachers' narrations, explored their coping mechanisms in addressing students' tardiness, and studied teachers' perceptions of using digital technology in classroom instruction and the theme of differentiated instruction. Additionally, it became apparent that the successful implementation of digital technology in classroom instruction required teacher training and adequate resources and support from school administrators. Our last emerging theme was the Lack of interactive teaching, a new quality of learning, and teaching was an absolute priority for education. Teachers were not only sources of information but also meant to lead managers

and teachers in developing interactions among students and training/developing critical social personality traits. The students want to understand natural phenomena, know scientific truths, and acquire knowledge to be applied in practice; for these reasons, they are dissatisfied with traditional education. Teachers are coping with the challenges faced in the new regular face-to-face classes, with a first theme emerging: Digital Teaching as an Innovative Strategy. Academic success has long been associated with attendance. Students who attend class regularly are more likely to understand better course material, participate more actively in class discussions, and achieve higher grades. Regular attendance also helps students develop time management skills and a sense of responsibility. Regular attendance exposes students to a structured learning environment that promotes their progress in all aspects. Technology has proven to catalyze positive change in education, and monitoring student attendance is no exception. In transitioning from manual methods to technology-driven solutions, many benefits can be gained, including improved accuracy, efficiency, student engagement, and early intervention opportunities. Preventing absenteeism ensures students stay on track academically and achieve their goals. Setting clear expectations for attendance and communicating these expectations to students and their families can help prevent absenteeism. Communicate consequences for unexcused absences and allow students to make up missed

work. Building positive relationships with students increases their motivation to attend class. Take time to get to know your students, provide support and encouragement, and create a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment. Providing engaging and interactive instruction can help keep students motivated and interested in attending class. Use various teaching methods, such as group activities, discussions, and hands-on projects, to keep students engaged and interested. Regular attendance monitoring and following up with absent students can help identify and address potential issues before they become chronic. Reach out to students who miss class to offer support, provide make-up work, and identify any potential barriers to attendance. Students at risk of absenteeism may benefit from additional support and resources. This may include tutoring, mentoring, counseling, or other interventions to help students stay on track and succeed academically. Collaboration with families and the wider community can help prevent absenteeism. Communicate regularly with families about attendance expectations, provide resources and support, and work together to identify and address any barriers to attendance. Educators can help ensure students have the support and resources they need to stay engaged and successful in school by proactively preventing absenteeism. Also, the results of this study highlight the attention and importance given by teachers to the learners to help aid the students during the pandemic.

4.1. Implications—Based on the results of this study, the implications for teachers are that the impact of teachers' experiences in addressing student tardiness face-to-face may include technical issues. Teachers' experiences addressing the students' tardiness in face-to-face classes revealed three emerging themes: To explore the teachers' experiences regarding students' tardiness, emerging themes were de-

veloped; establishing a Routine was the first theme in teachers' experiences addressing tardiness. The second theme is Creating a Positive Culture. Another theme is the teachers' experiences addressing tardiness in the new face-to-face format. The participants shared that creating a positive culture inside the classroom involves introducing values, norms, and standards to the students. lastly, there is a Lack of inter-

active teaching. A new quality of learning and teaching is an absolute priority for education. Teachers are not only sources of information; they are also meant to lead managers and teachers in developing interactions among students and training/developing critical social personality traits. Explore Experiences of Teachers' Coping Mechanisms to Address the Students' Tardiness in Face-To-Face Classes. Two emerging themes were revealed: Digital Teaching as an Innovative Strategy, as academic success has long been associated with attendance. Students who attend class regularly are more likely to understand better course material, participate more actively in class discussions, and achieve higher grades. Regular attendance also helps students develop time management skills and a sense of responsibility. Regular attendance exposes students to a structured learning environment that promotes their progress in all aspects. While the second theme was In-Person Interaction. Another theme of the teacher's challenges in the new normal is the lack of in-person interaction with the learners. Preventing absenteeism ensures students stay on track academically and achieve their goals. Setting clear expectations for attendance and communicating these expectations to students and their families could help prevent tardiness. Communicate consequences for unexcused absences and allow students to make up missed work. This was insight from the interaction between the teacher, participants,

and me during the discussions. Building positive relationships with students increases their motivation to attend class. Take time to get to know your students, provide support and encouragement, and create a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment. Providing engaging and interactive instruction can help keep students motivated and interested in attending class. Collaboration with families and the wider community can help prevent absenteeism. Communicate regularly with families about attendance expectations, provide resources and support, and work together to identify and address any barriers to attendance. By proactively preventing tardiness, educators could help ensure students have the support and resources they need to stay engaged and successful in school. Also, the results of this study highlight the attention and importance given by teachers to the learners to help aid the students during face-to-face classes. Tardiness is an alarming issue among students that has far-reaching effects on both academic and interpersonal realms. The complex interplay of factors contributing to tardiness requires a multifaceted approach involving institutions, teachers, students, and parents. By acknowledging the research-supported causes and effects and implementing collaborative strategies, educational communities can foster a culture of punctuality that supports students' academic success and personal growth.

4.2. Future Directions—As the education system continues to evolve in response to face-to-face classes, there are several potential future directions on experiences of student tardiness in the face-to-face, including: Department of Education officials may help improve a school's reputation by addressing tardiness and setting clear punctuality expectations. The first action step is to get everyone at your school on the same page by establishing a campus-wide tardy pol-

icy. Clearly define expectations about being in class on time, what constitutes a tardy, and what the consequences are if a student is marked as tardy. This was different for every campus, but clear communication about these expectations would allow your school to create solid foundations for a culture of timeliness. The school head may emphasize the importance of punctuality. It may need to reiterate this in face-to-face classes, as tardiness can disrupt the flow of class

and impact the learning experience of other students. Encouraging time management skills: With the increased flexibility of remote and hybrid learning, students may need to develop more vital time management skills to balance their academic responsibilities with other commitments. The school head may lead in solving the issue of student tardiness requires collaboration between educational institutions, teachers, students, and parents. By implementing policies that prioritize punctuality and reinforcing these policies consistently, institutions can set the tone for a punctuality-conscious culture. School guidance counselors may help students guide their role in the school, remind them that their office handles school sanctions and penalties, and possibly call their parents' attention. They may also offer effective time management strategies and allow us to consider alternative learning options for students who struggle with punctuality. The teachers may remember that you cannot lower a student's grades for chronic tardiness or absences; you also cannot include "participation" as part of your grading criteria.

However, there were some productive ways that you could manage this sort of problem in the classroom; one of the best ways to generate respectful and professional behavior in your students is to model such respect: show up to class on time and prepared, use class time efficiently, and dismiss class on time. Make it clear that students should inform you in advance of any unavoidable absence. If students miss two or more classes, remind them of the Program policy and alert them to the severe consequences of missing class. Tell them that if they miss more classes, they may need to meet with the principal and that their standing in the class may be at risk. Remember that you cannot lower their grades for the absences, though their participation grade would be impacted by missed classes. To the policymakers, for planning and drafting future training and seminars for teachers to adequately address implementation gaps of utilizing the roles and responsibilities of principals in the teaching and learning process. Finally, to the fellow researchers who wanted to conduct a similar or comparative study.

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